

Biometric Technology in Securing the Internet Using Large Neural Network Technology

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Abstract : The article examines the methods of protection of citizens' personal data on the Internet using biometric identity authentication technology. It's celebrated their potential danger due to the threat of loss of base biometric templates. To eliminate the threat of compromised biometric templates is proposed to use neural networks large and extra-large sizes, which will on the one hand securely (Highly reliable) to authenticate a person by his biometrics, and on the other hand make biometrics a person is not available for observation and understanding. This article also describes in detail the transformation of personal biometric data access code. It's formed the requirements for biometrics converter code for his work with the images of "Insider," "Stranger", all the "Strangers". It's analyzed the effect of the dimension of neural networks on the quality of converters mystery of biometrics in access code.

Keywords : Biometric security technologies, Conversion of personal biometric data access code, Electronic signature, Large neural networks, quality of converters "Biometrics - the code", the E-government.

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